

The Olfactory Turn in Social Robotics Futuring of Human-Robot Sociality with *ScentDia*

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Abstract

The accelerating diffusion of social robots, far from merely signifying a technological innovation, marks a profound social transformation — one that risks destabilizing the fabric of human sociality. In this work, we address the challenge of making this transformation socially sustainable by proposing a transdisciplinary paradigm for social robotics. Combining robotics, art, and philosophy, we advance an epistemological, methodological, ethical, and aesthetic framework to design robots for difference and social coordination, rather than human imitation and substitution.

We articulate this paradigm — “building robots *not like us*, but *with us*” — through three main contributions: (a) the notion of a *peri-human design space*, which situates robots in a domain where their social presence and interactions are deeply different yet fundamentally compatible; (b) the concept of *perceptual identity markers*, which make robots’ otherness immediately recognizable to human senses; and (c) *futuring social robotics*, a methodology for creating and staging *robotic agents-to-come*, engaging us in the experience of prospective hybrid human–robot social ecosystems.

We ground this paradigm in *ScentDia*, an artistic social robot that establishes and explores olfaction as a perceptual, technological, and cultural scaffold for robotic social presence. Drawing on evolutionary roots of human sociality, *ScentDia* engages humans through a scent — neither biological nor human-like — that signals its robotic identity. As a pioneering robot with an olfactory identity marker, *ScentDia* invites us to rethink what it means to interact socially with robotic agents, and to confront a central question: what we want — and may — become in sharing our social world with these agents.

Keywords: Socially sustainable robotics; peri-human design space; perceptual identity marker; futuring social robotics; olfactory social robotics; robot olfactory presence; synthetic anthropology; synthetic ethics

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence is increasingly expected to operate in both physical and social environments. Yet its most advanced models face a fundamental limitation: without a body, generative systems struggle to handle physical tasks, language, and social interaction. This

embodiment gap — recently reiterated by generative AI pioneer Yann LeCun (2025) — is now seen as a critical threshold for future progress. The issue, however, is not new. Since the 1990s, the importance of embodiment for enhancing artificial systems has been emphasized by *embodied cognitive science* and related AI research (e.g., Pfeifer, Bongard, 2006). Today, this view resurfaces at the frontier of generative AI and robotics, where social interaction presents both a technical challenge and — as LeCun forecasts — a defining frontier for the coming “decade of robotics.”

In this article, we take LeCun’s forecast seriously, interpreting it as a sign of an impending historical rupture. Within the next 3 to 5 years — as he suggests — we may witness not just widespread deployment of robots, but a *Cambrian explosion* of an emerging category of robots. We refer here to a rapid proliferation of the so-called *social robots*: robotic agents capable of interacting with us through signals that are socially compatible with our own — such as gaze, gesture, posture, facial expressions, proxemics, and language (e.g., Damiano, 2021; Lehmann & Rossi, 2020). Developed since the late 20th century, these robots are particularly suited for socially meaningful roles — including education, companionship, and therapeutic mediation (e.g., Fong et al, 2003). Enhanced by generative AI and Large Language Models (Zhang et al., 2023), they can diffuse into our social spaces, both public and domestic, to the extent of co-shaping them into new, hybrid human–robot social environments.

The diffusion of social robots is not just another technological innovation. It marks a new phase in our social evolution, one that may transform how we see each other, how we relate, and how we understand ourselves as social beings. As these robots begin to inhabit our environments, the crucial question becomes not just how they operate, but *who* they are to us — and who we become by interacting with them. This brings into focus a novel and key dimension of responsibility in the age of robotics: a specific articulation of ecological sustainability that we call *social sustainability*, broadly understood as the capacity to preserve and support human social bonds.

Social sustainability is attracting increasing attention in AI research, often linked to ethical design, social inclusion, and fair access to resources aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (e.g., Redko, 2023). However, its specific development within the field of social robotics remains largely underexplored, despite growing awareness that AI systems are embedded in and transformative of social environments (Sætra, 2021). Given the specifically strong potential impact that social robots can have on our sociality (e.g., Šabanović, 2010; Jones, 2017; Seibt, 2018), we propose a shift in perspective. Unlike most treatments of social sustainability in AI, which focus on harm reduction or safeguards, we suggest that robotics should not merely minimize disruption but actively preserve and support the human social fabric — for example, by enabling new robotic social presences that foster connection.

In this article we respond to this challenge by focusing on olfaction as a sensory modality that can support robotic social presence in ways that do not rely on anthropomorphic

mimicry. In contrast to interactional channels often designed to approximate human expressivity (e.g., face, voice, gaze), scent can operate as a distributed and temporally extended cue that contributes to the texture of co-presence and recognition. In this approach, scent is not an embellishment but a material, cultural, and technological substrate through which a robot can signal identity while preserving difference. In focusing on olfaction, we do not claim that this modality uniquely shapes trust, memory, or affect, nor that it should be isolated from other perceptual channels in human–robot interaction. Rather, olfaction is considered at the level of interactional affordances, that is, in terms of how different sensory modalities enable different modes of relational engagement and social presence at the design level. This choice is therefore not grounded in causal comparison between modalities, but in the exploration of alternative, non-anthropomorphic ways of configuring robotic social presence. In this perspective, olfaction is not framed here as a uniquely privileged modality, but rather as a paradigmatic case through which the notion of perceptual identity markers can be explored within a broader, inherently multisensory framework of human–robot interaction.

The ambition of our work is to do that by advancing innovation on four interrelated levels — philosophical, implementational, artistic, and methodological — that collectively define the emergence of a new form of social robotics, which we call *olfactory social robotics*.

At the *philosophical level*, we propose a systemic, relational, and pluralist epistemology and ethics of social robotics. Based on previous work (e.g., Damiano & Dumouchel, 2020), we argue that social robots should be conceived as new social actors; namely, agents capable of participating in social coordination dynamics with humans on the basis of mechanisms that are different from ours. This view implies a radical reorientation of social robotics, which can be framed as a shift away from anthropomorphic mimicry, towards the exploration of what we call the *peri-human space*. We define this space as a design domain in which robots elicit social responses not by resembling us — that is, not through anthropomorphic mimicry or resemblance-driven cues — but by engaging us through modalities of social presence and interaction grounded in difference, yet capable of sustaining compatibility and even enriching interaction through functional complementarity. Within this space, we locate the future development of human–robot sociality; not as a simulation of human sociality, but as a new, hybrid form of social dynamics. This reorientation carries both epistemological and ethical implications. Social robots do not replace human actors, but act as relational partners — distinct agents capable of supporting and extending our capacity for social engagement. To operationalize the philosophical principles of the *peri-human design space*, we introduce the concept of a *perceptual identity marker*. This concept refers to a sensory signal that simultaneously manifests the robot’s distinct artificial identity and invites social engagement by leveraging evolved mechanisms of human social cognition — provided that such a signal is persistently associated with the robot across interactions and plays a primarily relational rather than merely functional role. It embodies the epistemological and ethical commitment

to difference as a resource: enabling relational compatibility while preserving clear distinctiveness.

At the *implementational level*, our approach is embodied in the robot *ScentDia*, the third iteration of the *Diamandini robotic series* by Mari Velonaki. Conceived within her long-term artistic exploration of robotic presence and intercorporeality, *ScentDia* develops Velonaki's idea of using olfactory stimuli as a medium for robotic social presence — a proposal that grounds the transdisciplinary research collaboration presented in this article. This direction was informed by biological, neurophysiological, and anthropological insights into the social and evolutionary role of olfaction, rearticulated here as a radical epistemological hypothesis. Scent can serve as a perceptual identity marker, capable of inviting social interaction while emphasizing the distinction between interactors. Unlike other features, scent operates across species boundaries and pre-dates voluntary verbal and nonverbal communication in the evolution of social life. From plants to animals, humans included, olfaction is tied to memory, recognition, affective engagement, and bonding. Grounded in our philosophical framework, *ScentDia* harnesses this archaic medium not to simulate human presence, but to introduce a new kind of robotic social actor — one that expresses its distinct identity through scent, not by evoking human, animal, or plant smells, but by generating an olfactory presence unique to its artificial nature.

At the *artistic level*, this implementational choice materialized in *ScentDia* as both a social robot and an art installation. Realized through collaboration between robotic art (Velonaki & Rye, 2016), olfactory artistic creation (Gerakinis, 2025), and philosophical-ethical design (Damiano, 2021), this robot embodies an aesthetic-epistemological operation: to create a sensory portal into future hybrid (human-robot) social relations. As an art installation, *ScentDia* is not merely shown; it is experienced, offering a space in which humans can encounter and reflect on the social actors of the future. Artistic creation becomes, here, a form of *future world-making* grounded in experience, interaction, and the material enactment of the human-robot social contexts to come.

At the *methodological level*, *ScentDia* initiates what we call a *future social robotics approach*. This robot was not designed to solve a predefined problem; it was conceived as a generative prototype — a space for experimenting with human-robot sociality. *Future social robotics* takes shape as a transdisciplinary research practice in which artistic, robotic, and philosophical exploration converge to anticipate and prototype forms of cohabitation with artificial agents that still have to come. This approach does not impose normative or pedagogical models, nor prescribes desired outcomes. Instead, it creates a context in which people can encounter new robotic social agents through lived interaction; a context where philosophy, ethics, and art collaborate to make future forms of human-robot coexistence both imaginable and experienceable. In this way, *future social robots* enables participants to position themselves critically and autonomously, not by instruction, but through direct engagement with emerging relational possibilities. This is not a neutral space, but a situated

context, designed to support experiential, reflective, and critical engagement with emerging interactional configurations.

This article should be read as a pre-HRI, hypothesis-generating contribution. It does not aim to isolate causal effects of olfaction, nor to provide experimental validation of specific interaction outcomes. It articulates a transdisciplinary design and research framework—referred to as *future social robotics*—whose purpose is to open and structure a field of inquiry that may subsequently be addressed through controlled and systematic HRI studies. Accordingly, the observations reported from *ScentDia*'s public exhibition are not presented as empirical evidence, but as situated, qualitative, and exploratory material, intended to indicate emerging forms of interaction and research directions rather than to support or test theoretical claims. In this sense, the contribution is positioned as complementary to experimental HRI approaches, not as an alternative to them.

We develop this vision in nine sections: *Section 2* outlines the philosophical groundings; *Section 3* presents the transdisciplinary research framework; *Section 4* situates *ScentDia* within robotic art and introduces its olfactory turn; *Section 5* establishes scent as a perceptual identity marker; *Section 6* reconstructs the olfactory design of *ScentDia*; *Section 7* discusses its premiere and exhibition, presenting field observations and prospective lines of inquiry in HRI; *Section 8* expands on perceptual markers in social robotics and presents an ethical model; *Section 9* concludes by positioning *ScentDia* as a programmatic instance of olfactory social robotics within the paradigm of building *robots with us, not like us*.

2. Robots with us, not like us

2.1 The Evolution of Social Robotics

Social robotics emerged in the late 1990s from two main trajectories: the embodiment turn in cognitive science and the rise of Human–Robot Interaction (HRI). The first responded to the crisis of the classical cognitivist paradigm, which conceived cognition as abstract symbol manipulation. In contrast, embodied approaches argue that cognition involves the agent's body and arises through situated interaction with their environment — including its social dimension (e.g., Shapiro, 2011). Within this view, intelligent artifacts are not *naked algorithms* but *complete agents*: robots that, having a body, can engage with the world and other agents through physical interaction. On these grounds, robotics became the site of a new AI paradigm: Social Embodied AI (e.g., Damiano & Dumouchel, 2024). This paradigm draws on the cybernetic “understanding by building” approach, which investigates natural processes by constructing and testing artificial systems that instantiate theoretical hypotheses (e.g., Cordeschi, 2002). Applied to social cognition, this “synthetic method” enables researchers to study social behaviors by building robotic agents as embodied models. In this approach, hypotheses about social behavior are embodied in robots, tested in interaction, and compared to natural processes — refining both theory and its implementation in the process (e.g., Damiano & Dumouchel, 2020).

The second trajectory, HRI, developed as an engineering response to the need for intuitive collaboration between humans and robots. It aimed to make robots more relatable by equipping them with socially meaningful behaviors. This shift marked a transition from the operator–machine paradigm to a co-worker paradigm introducing the notion of robots as “social partners” (e.g., Fong et al., 2003). Since the early 2000s, HRI has focused on designing socially interactive robots — systems engaging humans through cues such as gaze, facial expression, gesture, and proxemics. A key concept in this development has been “social presence”, defined as the robot’s ability to evoke in humans the feeling of “being in the company of another” (Heerink et al., 2008). Achieving this involved adapting core features of human sociality to the context of human–robot relationships, enabling the deployment of social robots in education, healthcare, hospitality, and entertainment.

Together, these two trajectories shaped social robotics and gave rise to two distinct epistemological approaches. Drawing on John Searle’s terminology, we have elsewhere referred to them as the *strong* and the *weak* approach to social robotics (e.g., Damiano & Dumouchel, 2024, 2026a).

The *strong* approach is grounded in the ambition to transfer social cognition to artificial agents. It frames social robotics as a scientific *understanding-by-building* endeavor, aiming to construct genuinely social agents by modeling animal or human cognitive features — such as the ability to understand emotions and intentions, or engage in meaningful dialogue. By contrast, the *weak* approach explicitly focuses on simulating social behaviors. Here, the target is not an agent that possesses social cognition, but a functional artifact — a robot that appears socially competent by performing behaviors that are socially effective, without reproducing their underlying mechanisms.

The *weak* approach builds on the transdisciplinary study of coordination dynamics in human–human and human–animal social interaction. Its aim is to equip robots with alternative, non-human mechanisms of participation in circuits of social signaling. From this perspective, social robotics defines itself as a technological enterprise: not the quest to reproduce human sociality, but to engineer systems capable of sustaining interaction through compatible, though different, modalities.

Paradoxically, however, in current developments, this distinction tends to invert. While the *strong* approach remains largely an unrealized scientific ambition, the *weak* approach succeeds in practice, shaping the actual diffusion of social robots in real-world settings.

2.2 Rethinking Social Robots in Relational Terms

Numerous studies have shown that robots developed within the weak approach are often recognized by human users as “social partners”. They are perceived neither as human or animal social beings, nor as mere objects, but as occupying an *in-between zone* defying traditional classifications (e.g., Kahn et al., 2002; Breazeal, 2003; Sung et al., 2007; Melson et al., 2009; Severson & Carlson, 2010; Xiao et al., 2021; Jung & Hahn, 2023; Toparlak, 2023). This ambiguity has prompted growing reflection on the need for new ontological categories capable of capturing the distinctive status of these agents.

An early and paradigmatic example is *Bartok Jr.* (Hegel, 2006), which mirrors users' emotions not by replicating human physiology, but via a speech-based system that infers affective states and expresses them through facial animation. The success of this and similar robots lies in their ability to participate in human social coordination — such as emotional mirroring — without reproducing the biological bases of human sociality.

These examples invite us to rethink how we define and evaluate social agency in robotics, exposing deeper conceptual tensions between the strong and the weak approach. As we have argued elsewhere (Damiano & Dumouchel, 2024; 2026a), the apparent inversion between the two can be interpreted in different ways. One might explain the practical success of weak robotics as the result of lower technical demands. Yet a more compelling interpretation points to a deeper epistemological insight: the need to move beyond an individualistic conception of sociality.

Indeed, the current strong/weak distinction assumes sociality to be a set of individual properties that could, in principle, be transferred to artificial systems. In contrast, a systemic perspective conceives sociality not as something an agent possesses, but as a relational phenomenon that emerges through dynamic interaction (e.g., Bateson, 1972; Varela, 1995; Dumouchel, 1995; Gallese, 2009).

On these grounds, we argue that sociality is an agent's ability to participate in circuits of social signals — such as gaze, posture, timing, and expression — which coordinate the interactors by aligning or opposing their actions (e.g., Damiano & Dumouchel, 2020, 2024). From this perspective, the success of the weak approach becomes theoretically significant. The strong approach, still tied to an individualistic paradigm, appears conceptually limited in addressing the relational complexity of social life. In contrast, the weak approach — though originally intended as merely functional — emerges as stronger than the strong, in two relevant ways.

First, it can be interpreted not only as a technological endeavor but also as a scientific one: an implicit application of the *understanding-by-building* method, not at the level of individual cognition, but at the level of interindividual coordination. As we have shown in previous work on the epistemology of synthetic modeling (Damiano & Dumouchel, 2020), weak social robots function as scientific models of social interaction dynamics — not of their biological substrates. They embody hypotheses about how social coordination works, which are typically tested through empirical studies of human–robot interaction.

Second, building on this insight, the weak approach succeeds where the strong approach does not. That is: it produces genuine artificial social actors. From a systemic and relational standpoint, weak social robots can be recognized as novel and distinct kinds of social agents: artificial agents capable of participating in coordination dynamics with humans via mechanisms that differ from those of human or animal interactors (e.g., Damiano & Dumouchel, 2020, 2026a).

This reconceptualization suggests that defining social robots cannot be a priori or absolute, but must be situated and empirical — shaped by context, users, and interactions. Whether

or not a robot is social depends on the circumstances, not on a fixed set of internal features. Accordingly, the criteria for evaluating social robots must also shift. From a systemic-relational perspective, what matters is not whether a robot possesses human-like social capacities, but whether it contributes to the formation of social dynamics through signaling and coordination. In this view, the question is not whether a robot *is* social in itself, but whether it *does* sociality in context.

We believe this approach better reflects how humans relate to robots and effectively supports their integration into our evolving social landscapes. It introduces diversity and pluralism into the taxonomy of social agents, recognizing that artificial systems *need not* — and, as we argue, *should not* — reproduce human sociality in order to engage with us meaningfully. On these grounds, it also opens the way for a positive, critical ethical framework, moving beyond the merely prohibitive logic that too often dominates ethical discourse on social robots.

2.3 Synthetic Anthropology and Ethics

Seen from a relational perspective, weak social robotics — the approach currently driving the diffusion of robots in real-world settings — reveals a different picture of our future with social robots. The large-scale diffusion that lies ahead — a trajectory already envisioned by leading AI researchers such as LeCun — appears not only as a socially impactful wave of technological innovation, but also as a vast *understanding-by-building* experiment, continuously testing hypotheses about us and our sociality. Each social robot deployed in private or public contexts embodies assumptions about social coordination, turning its integration into an exploration of those assumptions in real-world conditions.

From this perspective, implementational social robotics is not just a branch of engineering, but an *understanding-by-building science* — a “synthetic anthropology”. That is: an experimental practice that studies us, humans, and our forms of sociality by constructing robotic agents capable of interacting with us (e.g., Damiano & Dumouchel, 2018). Crucially, this anthropology is not only epistemic but also transformative. It concerns not only who we are as social beings, but who we are becoming — and who we may wish to become — through the creation, deployment, and integration of robotic social agents. This process of self-transformation is not only individual, but also cultural and systemic, reshaping societal boundaries. In this sense, “weak” social robotics becomes a means of self-knowledge through a dynamic of self-transformation.

As robotic agents enter our interactional spaces, they inevitably affect how we perceive ourselves, how we relate to others, and how we shape our shared social world. This transformation leads us toward a future that, far from merely extending the present (Morton, 2018), is *deep future* — genuinely open-ended, co-constructed, and uncertain. Indeed, we cannot fully predict or grasp the unfolding of the changes produced by social robots, because the very process through which we come to better understand ourselves is also the process through which we transform ourselves by creating, deploying, and engaging with them.

The key question, then, is whether this dynamic can be steered toward social sustainability. We believe the answer is yes. It is possible to generate virtuous loops between what we learn about ourselves through social robots and how we evolve through our engagement with these machines. And we believe this potential extends directly to the ethical domain. The first lesson of *synthetic anthropology* is that robots can become social actors by participating in relational coordination through alternative, non-human mechanisms. This insight breaks the anthropocentric monopoly on social agency and enables a shift from purely negative ethical framings to a constructive paradigm.

These dominant framings — which we have elsewhere described as purely negative ethics (e.g., Damiano & Dumouchel, 2018, 2026a, 2026b) — are typically articulated around risks of substitution and deception (e.g., Danaher, 2019; Torras, 2024). While often motivated by legitimate concerns, these critiques express predominantly precautionary framings. They are formulated after robots have been developed, yet offer little capacity to influence their design in meaningful or generative ways. Worse, their purely prohibitive logic and lack of constructive engagement risk leaving social robotics without dedicated ethical guidance, thereby opening the field to market-driven dynamics or *ad hoc* value systems.

This calls for a “synthetic ethics”. Building on the epistemological shift from individualistic to relational models of sociality, *synthetic ethics* extends the *understanding-by-building* paradigm into the ethical domain (Damiano & Dumouchel, 2026a; 2026b). It emerges as a transdisciplinary and proactive engagement — to be integrated in the practice of social robotics — aimed at transforming encounters between humans and under-construction robotic agents into an opportunity for empirical inquiry. These encounters become experimental situations through which we can better understand how we behave, feel, and co-orient in the presence of artificial social others — and, simultaneously, refine the ethical dimension of robot design in response to those situated dynamics. Synthetic ethics, in this sense, is not a normative stance based on predefined principles, but a methodological framework: a way to construct ethical meaning and relevance in context, through interaction. It transforms the uncertainty surrounding emerging human–robot relations not into a problem to be solved once and for all, but into a generative space of reflection, orientation, and co-evolution.

The core ethical principle that synthetic ethics inherits from synthetic anthropology is this: if robots are recognized as different kinds of social actors, then they cannot and should not be conceived as substitutes for humans, nor merely as simulators, but as participants in our evolving social landscapes. This principle, far from being rhetorical, provides a concrete criterion for evaluating the social sustainability of robotics, as defined earlier in this article: a robot is socially sustainable when it contributes to the preservation and strengthening of the human social fabric. This emphasizes the ethical importance of *differentiation* between humans and artificial agents. Because social robots operate through different mechanisms and give rise to different forms of interaction, they should not aim at mimicry, but at

compatible alterity — forms of difference that can sustain relational engagement without confusion. *Designing for difference, not imitation*, avoids risks of negative ethical framings: illusion of human presence, erosion of authentic relations, and role replacement. It is also what enables robots to engage us meaningfully, while contributing to the diversity, intelligibility, and resilience of the social world.

2.4 Towards implementation: peri-human design space and perceptual markers

To move concretely beyond mimicry, we translate the philosophical framework described above into two epistemological and ethical notions for the design of social robots.

The first is the concept of *peri-human design space*, defining a design domain in which robots engage with humans not by reproducing human features, but by activating relational dynamics through distinct modalities of presence. The prefix *peri-* (from the Greek *peri*, meaning “around” or “near”) indicates a space that approaches the human without coinciding with it: a liminal zone in which social interaction can be sustained through compatible difference rather than resemblance. Within this space, difference becomes a design resource, enabling robots to participate in social coordination without relying on anthropomorphic simulation. By *difference as a resource*, we mean the deliberate use of non-human forms of presence as a positive design constraint, guiding social interaction without relying on resemblance or imitation.

The second is the concept of *perceptual identity marker*, defined as a deliberately designed sensory signal that manifests the robot’s artificial identity while anchoring interaction in evolved mechanisms of social cognition. Crucially, a perceptual identity marker does not correspond to any sensory feature *as such*, but to the relational function a signal performs: sustaining a recognizable and coherent interactional identity across encounters. Such markers render a robot’s alterity intelligible and socially readable, without inducing illusion or confusion about its ontological status.

At this stage, both notions should be understood as heuristic rather than operational. A useful parallel can be drawn with Masahiro Mori’s original formulation of the uncanny valley (Mori, 1970), which did not introduce measurable design criteria, but articulated a robust relational phenomenon. Mori identified a breakdown of familiarity arising when an artefact elicits strong social expectations that it cannot coherently sustain across modalities and over time—an effect he explicitly shows to be intensified by movement. As Mori emphasized, the issue is not human likeness *per se*, but the instability of social affinity produced when perceptual, behavioral, and temporal cues fail to align (Mori, 1970).

Reframed in relational terms, this insight suggests that familiarity is not a function of resemblance, but of whether an encountered agent remains socially readable and predictable within coordination dynamics (Dumouchel & Damiano, 2017; Damiano & Dumouchel, 2018; 2024; 2026a). In this sense, uncanny responses can be interpreted as disruptions of social coordination rather than as reactions to difference as such. The peri-human design space and perceptual identity markers are introduced in this same epistemic spirit: not as prescriptions or metrics, but as orienting principles that redirect design away

from mimicry and toward *compatible difference*—forms of recognizably non-human presence capable of stabilizing interaction without generating the perturbing ambiguities typically associated with near-human simulation.

This stance is explicitly differentiated from anthropomorphisation-based accounts of human–robot engagement (e.g., Epley et al., 2007), which primarily frame social attribution as a projection of human traits (e.g., Damiano & Dumouchel, 2018). In contrast, the peri-human design space proposed here treats sociality as emerging from social coordination grounded in difference rather than similarity, without relying on the attribution of human-like properties to the robot.

Potential instantiations of perceptual identity markers include non-biological tactile feedback, thermal or auditory signals, rhythmic micro-movements; and, as explored in the present project, olfactory cues as a paradigmatic exploratory case. As anticipated, in *ScentDia*, we focus on scent as a perceptual identity marker that operates across species boundaries and evokes deep relational responses linked to processes of memory, recognition, and affect. Olfaction here is not introduced as a privileged or exclusive modality, but as one instance of a broader class of relational markers, operating at the level of atmosphere, temporality, and affective orientation to sustain a coherent relational presence across interactions, while remaining explicitly non-human.

Together, these principles support differentiated interaction and help address the key risks often emphasized by critical ethical framings—namely, deception and substitution—not through exclusion, but through design. By fostering perceivable and intelligible difference, peri-human design contributes to socially sustainable forms of human–robot coexistence, grounded in pluralism rather than imitation.

A systematic theoretical and applicative development of the relations between peri-human design, the uncanny valley, and pluralist models of social coordination lies beyond the scope of the present article and constitutes the focus of ongoing work. Here, we concentrate on articulating and exploring these notions within an explicitly exploratory and synthetic research framework, using *ScentDia* as a situated case through which such principles can be enacted and examined. The next section outlines the transdisciplinary research framework within which these principles have been developed and explored.

3. Framing the Approach: Artistic and Philosophical Research in Futuring Social Robotics

3.1 Social Robotics as a Site for Synthetic Exploration

Building on the philosophical grounding above, *ScentDia* adopts a synthetic approach that mobilizes artistic and philosophical research to explore future human–robot ecologies. This mode of inquiry does not rely on standard validation protocols or fixed hypotheses, but constructs situated scenarios in which alternative relational configurations can be enacted, experienced, and critically examined.

Traditional HRI research typically unfolds within experimental paradigms aimed at evaluating performance, acceptance, and efficacy. While such methods are essential for applied development, they are limited in scope when it comes to exploring radical conceptual shifts. Social robotics — especially when approached from a relational, pluralist perspective — requires a broader epistemological space; a domain in which interaction is not only tested, but invented, and where meaning is not measured, but co-emerges, allowing for the exploration of relational configurations capable of supporting socially sustainable forms of cohabitation. In this sense, the futuring approach we adopt represents an explicitly preliminary phase, complementary to HRI: it creates open scenarios in which unanticipated forms of interaction can emerge and be qualitatively observed. These experiential insights constitute a first step that will subsequently inform the design of systematic HRI studies, where hypotheses shaped by this exploratory stage can be evaluated under controlled conditions.

On these grounds, we approach social robotics as a synthetic research laboratory: a domain in which robotic artefacts function as instruments for probing and reflecting on human sociality, intersubjectivity, and cohabitation. In this perspective, the robot is not a solution to a predefined problem, but a generative perturbation—a novel form of social presence that opens fundamental questions such as: What counts as a social being? What forms can social co-existence take? These questions are structurally open and cannot be exhaustively specified in advance. For this reason, they cannot be addressed through predefined experimental metrics alone, but require an initial phase of situated, exploratory inquiry focused on lived experiences of social engagement— affective, aesthetic, cognitive, and relational. Such exploratory work is not an alternative to experimental HRI, but a necessary condition for articulating the hypotheses, variables, and evaluative criteria that subsequent empirical studies can meaningfully investigate. Accordingly, this contribution is intentionally positioned as *pre-metric* rather than *anti-metric*. It precedes and informs experimental HRI research by articulating concepts, interactional variables, and design questions that subsequent quantitative and controlled studies can meaningfully investigate. This transdisciplinary orientation builds upon the synthetic approach introduced, in *Section 2*, as well as to the emerging notions of synthetic anthropology and synthetic ethics. Rooted in the principle of *understanding-by-building*, the synthetic approach has developed across multiple domains — from early cybernetics to embodied AI, Artificial Life, and synthetic biology — as a methodology that does not aim to replicate existing natural phenomena in their entirety. Instead, it constructs material systems — robotic, computational, chemical, or hybrid — that enact theoretical hypotheses under specific constraints, enabling the investigation of the generative mechanisms underlying life, cognition, and sociality as they are and as they could be (Langton, 1989; Damiano & Stano, 2023).

While sharing with speculative and critical design an interest in opening alternative futures (Dunne & Raby, 2013), futuring social robotics differs in that it is explicitly oriented toward the material prototyping of social interaction. The aim is to generate situated,

hypothesis-forming insights that can subsequently inform future HRI research, rather than primarily producing critical or discursive interventions.

In this framework, artistic and philosophical robotics converge in a specific form of synthetic research: a mode of inquiry that uses artificial agents as operational models to explore how forms of sociality could emerge under alternative configurations. These systems do not simulate sociality as it is, but instantiate possible modes of social human–robot interaction, in which new forms of presence and (perceptual, affective, experiential, rational) intersubjective exchange become thinkable.

This futuring modeling is what allows *ScentDia* to inhabit what we called, in *Section 2*, the peri-human design space: a zone of design that resists anthropomorphic mimicry and instead probes new modes of intersubjective coupling across ontological boundaries. In this sense, the robot becomes an epistemological artifact — a “revealing machine” in Pickering’s sense (2010) — that embodies philosophical propositions about social presence, otherness, and co-evolution. Its primary epistemic value does not lie in functional performance, but in its capacity to disclose new experiential, conceptual, and implementative trajectories for future sociality. This approach resonates with and extends ongoing initiatives at the intersection of art, technology, and research — such as S+T+ARTS (European Commission, 2016), Making Futures (2024), the Manifesto of Artistic Research (Henke et al., 2020), SymbioticA (Morisson, 2018), and Art-Based Research (Leavy, 2020), among others — while articulating a distinctive epistemological and ethical paradigm. Building on the valuable pathways these initiatives have opened for integrating artistic inquiry and technological innovation, our approach further foregrounds the epistemological and ethical stakes of social robotics, treating artistic and philosophical research as constitutive of a synthetic methodology that interrogates and prototypes socially sustainable human–robot ecologies.

3.2 Research Questions and Orientation

In light of this framework, the *ScentDia* project is guided by a set of open-ended questions rather than fixed hypotheses. The following questions orient the synthetic — artistic and philosophical — inquiry at the core of this research.

- What new forms of social presence can emerge through olfactory interaction between humans and non-human agents?
- How can scent become a medium of social distinction, rather than mimicry, and of connection, in the design of social robots?
- In what ways can robotic agents contribute to reconfiguring the boundaries of the human and the social?
- What aesthetic, affective, experiential, and rational dimensions are activated in human encounters with non-anthropomorphic but sensorially expressive robotic machines?
- Can olfactory identity support new modes of socially sustainable co-evolution between humans and artificial agents?

These questions are not meant to delimit a field of inquiry, but to open it. They function as exploratory direction-markers, orienting the design and interpretation of *ScentDia* while leaving space for emergence, uncertainty, and pluralism.

3.3 An Exploratory Practice

At this stage, futuring social robotics adopts a non-prescriptive and exploratory stance. It does not aim to assess whether a given interaction conforms to predefined models of social behavior or desired norms. Instead, it creates situated conditions under which new forms of interaction — including ambiguous, gentle, or unexpected ones — can emerge and be experienced. Rather than evaluating outcomes, this approach explores how meaning, presence, and social patterns may begin to take shape during open-ended human–robot encounters.

At this exploratory stage the robot is not evaluated according to performance metrics or user satisfaction. Its epistemic value lies not in what it confirms, but in what it proposes: the kinds of interactions, dynamics, and perspectives it helps make visible. The artistic–philosophical installation is not intended for usability testing, but for embodying and staging hypotheses. It constitutes a space in which possible future forms of interaction can begin to take shape in view of socially sustainable forms of human–robot co-existence.

Accordingly, in this phase, the *ScentDia* project does not investigate human–robot interaction in the classical experimental sense; rather, it offers a concrete setup in which a possible mode of social interaction may emerge. It is a proposal, not a prototype to be optimized. Its aim is to stimulate reflection, open dialogue, and set the stage for further exploration. In this sense, the robot functions not as a solution to a given problem, but as a catalyst — initiating lines of inquiry into new possibilities for social interaction.

In line with this stance, the premiere of *ScentDia* and its ten-day exhibition were approached through a naturalistic, unobtrusive, and exploratory qualitative observation. The resulting field notes, presented in *Section 7.4*, do not constitute empirical evidence of interactional effects; rather, they provide situated and preliminary insights into how the robot’s scent-based presence was perceived, engaged with, or disregarded by visitors. This exploratory material is treated as hypothesis-generating, informing the next phase of our work: the development of systematic HRI studies under controlled conditions, specifically designed to examine and test interactional hypotheses identified at this exploratory stage.

4. Creating *ScentDia*: The *Diamandini Series* at an Olfactory Turn

4.1 The Diamandini Series: Crafting Peri-Human Robotic Presence

The *Diamandini series* (2011–2025), initiated by Mari Velonaki, represents a long-term artistic and epistemological exploration of robotic presence, affect, and intercorporeality. From its inception, the series has interrogated the physicality that is possible and acceptable

between a human and a robot, employing materiality, ambiguity, and slowness as relational strategies.

The first *Diamandini robot* (2011), developed with support from the Australian Research Council, was realized within interdisciplinary research at the Australian Centre for Field Robotics (University of Sydney). Conceived as an interactive robotic installation, it was designed to propose a new sculptural robotic form that uses implicit modes of communication such as movement (*Fig. 1*).

The robot's sculptural figure — with a porcelain-like finish — introduced a new aesthetic in robotics, diverging from stereotypical humanoid robots while echoing the human form (Velonaki & Rye, 2016). To achieve its ethereal, gliding motion, a novel omnidirectional motion base was invented and patented, enabling smooth, rolling movement even when changing direction or velocity.

Diamandini's subtle, non-verbal gestures, its material ambiguity, and its deliberately slow movements created an unsettling yet compelling sense of presence, resisting anthropomorphic mimicry while sustaining social tension and curiosity. In this framework, the robot was not a tool but a crafted vessel of *embodied otherness*, capable of generating complex affective dynamics without explicit verbal or gestural communication — an early gesture toward designing in the *peri-human* space, where difference becomes a resource for relational engagement.

Over time, the series evolved from a focus on direct physical proximity to an exploration of ambient and distributed presence. The second iteration, *Diamandini Revisited: In Conversation...* (2024), was commissioned for the opening of the new National Communications Museum in Melbourne and developed at the Creative Robotics Lab (National Facility for Human-Robot Interaction Research, University of New South Wales, UNSW, Sydney). In this version, sonic presence was introduced: a distributed sound system with personalized sonic responses allowed *Diamandini* to engage in a dialogic exchange with *George the Australian Speaking Clock* (1954), while navigating their shared museum environment (Velonaki, 2024; Robinson et al., 2023). This was the first time a robotic body created a dynamic, distributed soundscape, with movement and sound intertwined in real time (*Fig. 2*).

This setup explored the temporal and sonic resonance between the robot and its environment, with *Diamandini* responding to *George's* time announcements through finely timed micro-gestures and sound. The resulting interaction shifted the register from embodied expressivity to perceptual coupling, introducing an early form of what we now call *peri-presence* — a mode of robotic presence grounded in co-sensing, resonance, and multi-sensory engagement.

Figure 1. *Diamandini* (2011), the inaugural piece of the *Diamandini series*.

4.2 *ScentDia*: Diamandini’s Olfactory Turn

Developed in 2025 as part of the *Diamandini series* (Creative Robotics Lab, National Facility for Human-Robot Interaction Research, UNSW, Sydney), *ScentDia* introduces olfactory stimuli as a novel medium for crafting robotic presence — one that unfolds as a multisensory constellation of movement, sound, and scent.

This approach aligns with a broader trajectory of olfactory experimentation across art, technology, and robotics.

Japanese artist Hiroshi Koyama has developed a body of work centered on olfactory sculptures (e.g., Jaquet, 2022; Olfactory Research Network, 2022). These works use ancient minerals and handcrafted forms to evoke “the scent of time” and invite reflection on memory, transformation, and affective resonance. While Koyama’s installations engage olfaction through static, contemplative arrangements, *ScentDia* extends this exploration into dynamic interaction: scent becomes a moving agent, performed by a robot and inscribed in both spatial and social ecologies.

This cultural turn is also evident in immersive media. For instance, in February 2025, Andrew Rogers (2025) described a virtual reality game that integrates scent to intensify emotional immersion and environmental realism, illustrating a growing cultural interest in olfaction as a medium of experiential depth and interactional nuance. However, whereas such games primarily use scent as a perceptual enhancement to simulate existing environments and amplify user experience, *ScentDia* takes a different, more generative stance. It uses olfactory expression not to replicate, but to create and perform new relational dynamics between humans and robots, making scent an active social signal rather than a mere atmospheric effect.

In parallel, advances in robotics have explored olfactory perception, integrating insect-inspired electroantennogram sensors for scent-based navigation (Martínez et al., 2014). Unlike perceptual systems that passively detect odors, *ScentDia* actively emits scent as a social presence, imprinting itself through olfactory signals that permeate the shared space. Olfaction here is neither decorative nor metaphorical; it functions as a perceptual identity marker, simultaneously inviting interaction and signaling otherness. This asymmetry — between active and passive olfaction, as well as between human and robot sensory modalities — is crucial for our synthetic inquiry. It allows *ScentDia* to move beyond models focused on recognition or mimicry, enabling new forms of interaction based on difference and mutual responsiveness.

Figure 2. *Diamandini Revisited: In Conversation...* (2024), extending the series into distributed sonic presence within a museum environment.

5. Scent and Sociality: Towards Olfactory Social Robotics

5.1 Olfaction as a Cross-Species Social Language

Long overlooked in favor of vision and speech, olfaction remains one of the most archaic and pervasive modes of social signaling — from plants to mammals. Plants use volatile organic compounds to chemically signal to neighbors about threats, resources, or pollinators, enabling forms of proto-social interaction grounded in evolutionary coordination that do not require nervous systems (Pierik et al., 2012; Conchou et al., 2019). This chemical dialogue represents a primordial form of sociality, emphasizing presence and interaction beyond symbolic cognition.

In mammals, olfactory cues serve as crucial conveyors of social information, signaling identity, reproductive status, kinship, and emotional states essential for regulating social behaviors such as mating, cooperation, and parenting (Brennan & Kendrick, 2006). These signals are processed by neural circuits intimately linked to memory and emotion centers — notably the amygdala and hippocampus — that underlie social recognition and bonding (Ferguson et al., 2001; Almeida-Santos et al., 2019).

Humans, despite having fewer olfactory receptor genes than many mammals, have evolved an olfactory system finely tuned to social cognition, emotion, and memory (Shepherd, 2004; Jacobs et al., 2015). The anterior cingulate cortex and orbitofrontal cortex play pivotal roles in integrating olfactory information with attention, emotion, and decision-making (García-Cabezas & Barbas, 2014; Zald & Pardo, 1997). This specialization supports nuanced social interactions beyond mere survival functions.

Critically, olfaction provides a key mechanism for individual differentiation within social groups. Mammals use specific chemosensory signatures — often linked to genetic markers — to recognize and discriminate between conspecifics, facilitating social cohesion and cooperation (Spehr et al., 2006). In humans, olfactory cues similarly influence interpersonal attraction, kin recognition, and emotional contagion, playing a role in shaping social bonds and group identity (Cann & Ross, 1989; Olsson et al., 2006).

Compared to interactional channels that are often designed as explicit signals (e.g., facial animation, gaze behaviors, or vocal prosody), olfaction can function as a distributed and lingering cue, contributing to memory, recognition, and affective tone in ways that are not easily reduced to discrete symbols. These features offer distinct affordances for social robotics, enabling the design of relational agents that can signal identity, modulate affect, and sustain social atmospheres over time in situated contexts.

5.2 Olfaction as Scaffolding for Identity, Difference, and Ethical Sociality

Building on olfaction’s cross-species role, we see scent not merely as an additional sensory modality, but as a scaffold for human–robot sociality. Importantly, this scaffold operates within an inherently multisensory interactional field: olfactory cues in *ScentDia* are never

isolated from visual, auditory, or spatial perception, but co-constitute a distributed sensory ecology through which social presence is enacted. This perspective aligns with philosophical accounts of multisensory perception, which emphasize that perceptual experience is constituted through integrated, cross-modal processes rather than isolated sensory channels (O’Callaghan, 2016). Accordingly, olfaction is treated here not as an isolated stimulus, but as one component of an integrated sensory field through which robotic presence becomes perceptually and socially legible.

Olfactory cues operate on multiple levels: they provide immediate signals that orient and bond individuals, and they also create pervasive “semantic atmospheres” — background sensory environments that subtly influence emotions and social dynamics, often without conscious awareness. These atmospheres shape the shared social space, fostering trust, reducing stress, and modulating emotional alignment (Kiyokawa et al., 2012; Croijmans et al., 2022). On these grounds, we understand scent as a core ingredient of a distributed form of robotic presence — one that extends beyond direct interaction to shape relational dynamics throughout the environment, supporting new modes of social engagement.

In robotics, olfaction has so far been limited primarily to environmental perception and odor detection, while expressive and relational deployment of scent remains largely unexplored. The *ScentDia project* represents an exploratory framework for human–robot social interaction, in which olfaction functions not as mere decoration or symbolic adornment, but as a fundamental environmental and social affordance. The ambition is to provide the grounding for a new paradigm of olfactory social robotics, where scent becomes an active medium for robotic presence, human–robot social bonding, and the clear distinction between human and robotic identity.

Scent can produce clear differentiation between humans and robots. Olfactory cues support a robot’s identity as an “other” — a non-human social actor. This concept is intimately linked with the peri-human design space introduced earlier, which frames a domain of interaction grounded in difference and complementarity rather than mimicry. In *ScentDia*, this difference is operationalized through the notion of a perceptual identity marker: a sensory signal that affirms the robot’s distinct presence while enabling meaningful social coordination with humans. Through this mechanism, robots can engage in social interaction while maintaining identity transparency.

This design approach helps avoid the pitfalls highlighted by critical ethical framings and opens a pathway to socially sustainable human–robot co-evolution. Here, relationality is not simulated, but cultivated through sensory modalities that support both connection and alterity, marking a significant shift in how we conceive robotic social presence. We apply this approach to *ScentDia* as a robotic social actor, positioning it as a programmatic case within olfactory social robotics. In this perspective, scent does not add a decorative layer but specifies a design program. The following section translates this program into material decisions — fragrance identity, diffusion system, and interactional dynamics — realised in *ScentDia*.

6. Scenting a Social Robot: *ScentDia*'s Olfactory Identity, Presence and Interaction Dynamics

6.1 *ScentDia*'s Olfactory Identity: The Fragrance

The creation of *ScentDia*'s olfactory identity was developed within the project team through a dedicated design process led by olfactory designer Manos Gerakinis, founder of Manos Gerakinis Parfums, together with the perfume team of Vioryl (Gane et al., 2013). Rather than replicating familiar human fragrances, the goal was to produce a scent that could act as a perceptual identity marker, expressing social presence through a volatile atmosphere rather than visual or behavioral mimicry.

This opened the way for a novel practice of olfactory world-making, guided by historical imaginaries and cultural memory as much as by material and aesthetic considerations. In the absence of an established tradition of olfactory design in robotics, the team framed the fragrance as a symbolic and genealogical marker of presence, deeply intertwined with cultural and evolutionary narratives. Guided by the genealogical lineage of *ScentDia*, the fragrance reflects the robot's dual heritage: its form and robotic features conceived by Velonaki in Sydney, and its scent developed by Gerakinis in Athens. The fragrance is evocative and non-classifiable: blending cypriol and sandalwood to reference the robot's Australian origin, and oakmoss and citrus to symbolically link to Greece, where the olfactory identity was crafted. This olfactory composition draws on a symbolic reconstruction of Greek automata mythology — from Hephaestus and his golden maidens to the archaic kore figure that inspired the robot's aesthetics. These genealogical references informed the design narrative of the olfactory identity; they were not intended as interactional cues or as a basis for attributing human-like meaning during the exhibition. The scent emits a subtle metallic aura — both earthy and synthetic — designed not for conventional pleasantness but as a distributed atmospheric presence that marks the robot's passage in the perceptual field without relying on visual or linguistic cues.

This focus on sensory world-making intertwines material and aesthetic considerations with myth, history, and cultural memory — evoking new imaginaries of human–robot interspecies sociality. The design process of *ScentDia*'s olfactory identity marker exemplifies the project's commitment to synthetic research, employing a genealogical approach that interlinks sensory design with cultural and historical narratives. Ultimately, the fragrance of *ScentDia* functions not as a mere accessory but as relational scaffolding: it anchors the robot's presence in the social world while remaining open to interpretation. What was previously theorized as a perceptual identity marker is now materially embodied in scent, becoming a tangible and experiential medium that fosters relational distinction and recognition. While the fragrance articulated *ScentDia*'s cultural and symbolic identity, its deployment as a dynamic presence in the shared environment demanded a distinct technical and performative response — realized through the design of the scent system.

6.2 *ScentDia's Olfactory Presence: The Diffusion System*

ScentDia's scent system was conceived as a material experiment in *peri-presence*: a distributed, multisensory mode of presence that lingers in space and time, resonates with human perception, and asserts the robot's otherness — even when it has physically moved on. The system was designed not simply to add an olfactory element, but to create an *atmospheric landscape*: an asymmetric, temporal, transitory trace that extends the robot's presence beyond its body and inscribes it into the sensory ecology of the environment.

Designing such a presence meant overcoming significant constraints. Conventional delivery mechanisms — relying on alcohol, water, or heat — were excluded because they risked damaging electronics and flooding the space with an overpowering, uniform scent. To address these challenges, the Creative Robotics Lab developed a custom device that releases subtle, synchronized trails of scent aligned with the robot's movements and interaction cues. The emitter was deliberately positioned at the rear of the robot, enabling it to leave an olfactory trail as it moved through the environment. This decision ensured that the scent unfolded as a trace rather than a cloud, marking the robot's passage without saturating the space — and enhancing the asymmetry of its presence.

This rear-positioned, trailing emission reflects a deeper design logic. It materializes the idea of a robot that engages relationally without confronting directly, asserting its distinct identity through a presence that is felt rather than imposed. The design draws on biological paradigms of scent-marking and social signaling, where individuals leave traces that communicate identity, territory, and emotion beyond immediate contact. At the same time, it resonates with cultural practices such as the *sillage* of perfume — a crafted olfactory trail that evokes intimacy, memory, and difference. The scent system thus bridges biological, anthropological, technological, and artistic dimensions, inhabiting a peri-human space where natural and cultural registers intersect to create a novel form of social presence.

The resulting *scentscape* transforms key aspects of biological and cultural olfactory presence — persistence, diffusion, emotional resonance — into a uniquely robotic modality. As in previous iterations of the *Diamandini series*, where sound extended the robot's presence through distributed resonance, scent here unfolds atmospherically and temporally, engaging humans through a social signal that is unfamiliar yet legible. In doing so, the system enacts the principles of *perceptual identity marker* and *peri-human design*: it performs difference as a condition for connection, inscribing the robot's path in the interactional field and anchoring its presence within a multisensory social ecology.

More than a signal of identity, the scent system contributes to the emergence of a novel kind of social actor — an artificial participant in the multispecies ecology of interaction. By harnessing olfaction's cross-species power to evoke recognition, memory, and affect, the robot situates itself as a distinct yet compatible partner in human social life. This extension of olfaction — beyond its evolutionary roles and toward artificial agents — exemplifies the ambition of social robotics as articulated in this work: creating partners

that are different yet attuned, capable of co-shaping shared worlds through perceptual and affective resonance. In this sense, scent becomes not merely a medium of presence but a bridge — a sensory passage into a richer, more plural human–robot sociality.

6.3 Olfactory Interaction Design

Building on the *Diamandini series*' relational engagement — where approach and orientation depend on proximity and time spent in a shared space — *ScentDia* extends these principles into the olfactory domain. Rather than encoding anthropomorphic cues, interaction is organised around spatial–temporal relations that fit the peri-human design space: distance and duration shape how the robot makes itself perceptible.

Operationally, the scent module is integrated into the same control architecture that governs *ScentDia*'s omnidirectional motion and sound. The system does not modulate quantitatively the fragrance released; instead, it regulates emission frequency in relation to social parameters detected in the environment (visitor density, proximity, and dwell time). To avoid saturation, the robot maintains a short-term memory of recent emissions and combines it with data from external cameras that estimate the number and spatial distribution of people in the exhibition space. Because olfactory interaction is spatially distributed and accumulative, regulating emission frequency requires a global estimate of occupancy and flow to avoid plume build-up. Four external cameras provided stable full-field coverage of the exhibition area independently of the robot's self-motion, enabling consistent scheduling of short pulses and helping maintain a trailing *sillage*. External cameras were preferred over integrated vision because they ensured reliable coverage of the exhibition space, reduced the technical load on the robot, and privileged olfactory presence as the central medium of interaction, allowing scent emission to remain the primary channel through which social engagement was structured.

In line with this design, *ScentDia*'s responsivity does not rely on recognizing gestures, faces, or verbal input. Instead, its interaction is modulated by spatial–temporal parameters — such as proximity, dwell time, and occupancy patterns — which regulate how movement and olfactory emission are coordinated in the shared space. Accordingly, *ScentDia*'s interactional dynamics unfold through the following principles.

- *Temporal relational proximity*: the longer a visitor remains near the robot, the higher the likelihood of an emission, translating duration into a criterion for engagement.
- *Quality of movement*: smooth, non-obstructive trajectories by the visitors tend to elicit more fluid releases, whereas abrupt or disruptive movements can prompt the robot to reorient and move away.
- *Initiation of contact*: in the absence of approach for some time, the robot tends to emit while moving closer, marking its presence and inviting recognition.
- *Departure cue*: when the robot's path is blocked and it pivots away, a brief pulse can accompany the withdrawal, marking disengagement and making the exit more legible to those nearby.

These operational choices established the conditions for the situated observations reported in the next section, where we describe how visitors responded during the premiere and subsequent exhibition.

7. Staging Co-Presence: A Synthetic Ecosystem

7.1 Setting the Scene: *ScentDia* at the *Polene Hall*

The premiere of *ScentDia* (Fig. 3) took place on 21 February 2025 at the Museo Nazionale della Scienza e della Tecnologia “Leonardo da Vinci” in Milan. The robot was exhibited for ten days in the *Polene Hall*, a vast gallery dedicated to the carved figureheads of historical ships — an evocative space that shaped the perceptual atmosphere of the installation.

The public introduction to the project was held separately, in the *Count Biancamano Hall*, aboard the reconstructed bridge of the 1920s ocean liner permanently housed within the museum. This choice was not incidental. The setting recalled not only histories of maritime navigation, but also the deeper conceptual lineage that informs our project. Cybernetics — from the Greek *kybernētikḗ tékhnē*, the art of steering or navigating with the rudder — is the epistemological root of the synthetic approach and the foundational matrix of social robotics as a techno-scientific discipline. Born as a transdisciplinary field at the crossroads of biology, engineering, neurophysiology, psychology, and philosophy, cybernetics redefined scientific inquiry by shifting the focus from representation to construction, and from observation to interaction.

In choosing to present *ScentDia* aboard the reconstructed bridge of the *Count Biancamano Hall*, we reactivated this heritage. We embraced the metaphor of navigation not merely as spatial movement, but as a way of orienting ourselves within the evolutionary transition now underway — a bifurcation in human sociality brought about by the increasing presence of social robots. For us, steering — understood in its original sense of “navigating with the rudder” — means engaging with this transition reflectively, designing conditions for new forms of co-presence that are not based on mimicry, but on the creation of shared, perceptually meaningful worlds. This vision was shared with the public during the premiere, framing the event not only as an artistic unveiling but as a collective reflection on how to navigate our social future.

The setting also evoked a layered semantic field around the notion of *scia* or *sillage* — respectively, the Italian and French term for both the trail left by a moving vessel and the lingering trace of scent. This double resonance — between navigation and olfactory presence — encapsulated the project’s core operation. Inscribing an artificial agent not as a replica, but as a transient, atmospheric presence in a shared perceptual world.

Figure 3. *ScentDia* (2025), introducing olfactory presence in social robotics as a *perceptual identity marker*.

7.2 Designing the Synthetic Ecosystem

Consistently with the methodological framework (*Section 3*) and the interaction design (*Section 6*) adopted, the premiere was configured as a *situated synthetic ecosystem*, a dynamic and open environment where robotic and human agents shared a perceptual space. Instead of seeking validation through control, it foregrounded emergence, contingency, and co-presence as epistemological tools. The premiere became a live instance of synthetic research; a space in which knowledge is generated through the performative staging of relational possibilities.

The robot was positioned in a delimited interaction zone within the *Polene Hall*. A system of external cameras mapped the trajectories of visitors, allowing for autonomous movement based on their proximity and orientation. The scent was not emitted continuously, but released intermittently — synchronized with movement and ambient conditions — producing ephemeral markers of presence dispersed through the shared sensorium.

This configuration avoided any prescriptive choreography. Instead, it allowed new forms of interactivity to emerge, shaped by the aesthetic, spatial, and sensory affordances of the environment itself.

7.3 Atmosphere, olfactory proxemics, and relational knowledge

ScentDia's presence unfolded less as scripted turn-taking and more as atmospheric uptake: brief, frequency-modulated scent pulses reconfigured the shared field so that people recalibrated where to stand, how long to linger, and when to yield. We read this as “olfactory proxemics”: the structuring of distance, lateral alignment, and passage management through scent-timed cues and ambient flow. Olfactory proxemics is introduced here as a possible extension of proxemic theories — traditionally centered on visual, postural, and linguistic cues in human-robot interaction (Mumm & Mutlu, 2011) — to be explored through dedicated HRI studies, beyond the scope of the present paper.

Here, we focus on the interactional possibilities opened by *ScentDia*'s olfactory social presence. By engaging a sensory modality that is archaic, affectively potent, and resistant to representation, *ScentDia* activated a relational field grounded in asymmetry and ambiguity, which might be conceived as a form of *artificial empathy* (e.g., Damiano, 2026). In this register, the robot does not mirror human expressions; it modulates a trace in time, and humans respond with micro-adjustments of posture, pacing, and spacing. These circuits of human–robot affective signalling — where differences in the perception and expression of presence co-determine both parties' tendencies to respond — show that social interaction can emerge from shared, distributed, affectively coloured atmospheres.

7.4 Olfactory Interaction in Situ: Field Notes and Open Questions

In line with the methodological approach set out in *Section 3.3*, we kept exploratory, non-systematic observational field notes during the premiere and the subsequent ten-day exhibition. Guided by the olfactory interaction design principles defined in *Section 6.3*, we used the following behavioral dimensions as heuristic markers for observation.

- a) How did visitors approach or give way to the robot?
- b) How did visitors position themselves around the robot?
- c) How long did visitors maintain close proximity to the robot?
- d) How did visitors respond when the robot emitted scent (through brief, frequency-modulated pulses as previously described) or changed its trajectory?

Based on the collected observational material, we first tentatively outline recurrent interactional configurations across days, then illustrate them with specific short episodes, and finally outline avenues of inquiry that this material opens for a follow-up HRI study with *ScentDia*.

The following labels are used descriptively to organize recurrently noted interactional configurations. They do not imply stable categories, measured effects, or generalisable behavioural patterns. They function as provisional narrative framings that render situated observations legible within the theoretical framework introduced earlier, without attributing explanatory or evidential status to them.

A. Interactional configurations noted across the exhibition

- *Transition-coupled attribution*. In several observed instances, the scent was linked to the robot at transitions — during approach and, especially, withdrawal — when a brief trailing pulse marked its path, co-occurred with pointing or brief remarks about “the robot’s smell” before visitors moved on.
- *Wake tracking (“sillage windows”)*. After the robot passed, small clusters of visitors were observed to pause for a few seconds in its wake, inhaled the air, or adjusted position to cross the corridor the robot had just traversed.
- *Parallel co-presence at lateral offset*. Visitors were observed to pace alongside the robot at a stable side-by-side distance for several meters, adjusting their speed and orientation to that of the robot, without touch or speech — an alignment read here in relation to the peri-human stance.
- *Time as engagement*. Repeated presence in the robot’s vicinity (return passes or extended dwell) was noted to precede approach behavior and a short emission, in line with the frequency-based interaction described in *Section 6.3*.
- *Disengagement read as cue*. When the robot pivoted and left after its path was cut, a short trailing pulse often coincided with bystanders stepping aside and the new trajectory space reopening, making the robot’s exit possible.
- *Ambientisation under crowding*. At peak times, discrete pulses were less salient as single events and the scent settled into a diffuse background; nonetheless, proximal co-presence around the robot persisted.

- *Boundary cases.* In a minority of passes there was no visible reaction, consistent with ventilation and flow masking noticeability.

B. Illustrative episodes

The following episodes are presented as illustrative examples drawn from field notes, without claims of representativeness or frequency.

- *Close inspection by children.* During a primary-school visit (~15–20 children), several children approached the robot from behind (where the scent emission module is located), inhaled at close range during a short pulse, lingered, and asked repeated questions about “the robot’s smell,” reluctant to move on.
- *Playful interaction with explicit reference to scent.* A visitor kneeled and staged a marriage proposal to the robot after commenting on its smell, indicating addressability and role-ascription without facial or linguistic cues.
- *Interspecies curiosity.* Across multiple days, the resident museum cat repeatedly shadowed stretches of the robot’s recent path and paused where a trailing pulse had just been released (independently reported by museum staff overseeing the exhibition).

C. From futuring to HRI: questions opened by the observations

Coherently with our methodological approach, the material collected during the premiere and the ten-day exhibition must be understood as preliminary. These observational field notes provide qualitative, situated insights into how visitors engaged with *ScentDia*’s olfactory presence, but they should not be understood as systematic HRI data. Their role is not to validate, but to serve as an exploratory articulation within a futuring stage designed to open relational possibilities and to generate hypotheses to be tested. In this sense, the exhibition operated as a synthetic field laboratory: its contribution lies in making interactional patterns traceable and helping to orient the next phase of inquiry.

On this basis, we outline below a set of prospective lines of inquiry for future controlled HRI studies. Each point highlights a specific behavioral dynamic — such as olfactory proxemics, transition-based attribution, or side-by-side co-presence — that could be systematically tested through protocols with quantitative measures.

1. *Legibility at transitions.* Compare explicit source attribution when emissions are time-locked to approach/withdrawal versus untimed or silent passages.
Relevance: transitions concentrate attention and are the natural locus for a perceptual identity marker to be read without anthropomorphic cues — an entry point for olfactory proxemics.
2. *Co-presence structuring.* Assess whether emissions aligned with brief stillness co-occur with longer dwell and smaller lateral/forward offsets than misaligned cases.
Relevance: in a peri-human register, olfaction should scaffold side-by-side alignment and lingering; this directly operationalises olfactory proxemics.

3. *Withdrawal as coordination.* Test whether an emission at pivot-and-leave co-occurs with fewer crossings/blocks and quicker re-opening of space compared to silent withdrawal.

Relevance: beyond recognition, the marker should help organise turn-taking/traffic-like coordination — proxemic effects mediated by scent.

4. *Ecological bounds under crowding.* Characterise how occupancy modulates the salience of discrete pulses and their ambientisation.

Relevance: gallery constraints (ventilation, flow) bear directly on the frequency/memory logic in *Section 6.3* and on the limits of olfactory proxemics in public settings.

Operational details (timing conditions, distance bands, occupancy; attribution, dwell, minimum distance, duration of lateral co-presence, yielding/re-opening) will be specified in the dedicated HRI study to capture olfactory proxemics with precision. These hypotheses are intentionally framed at a conceptual level and will require dedicated experimental designs.

8. Expanding Robotic Social Presence through Perceptual Markers and Synthetic Ethics

8.1 Modulating Scent: From Identity to Co-regulation

In *ScentDia*, scent is not a fixed attribute but an emergent medium of presence, making the robot perceptually legible through atmospheric and affective resonance. While the current implementation provides a consistent olfactory identity, it also opens the way for more nuanced forms of modulation. Variations in intensity, rhythm, or spatial diffusion could express different modes of engagement: a soft, continuous presence might signal calm availability; a pulsed emission could indicate activation or transition; a localized release might mark approach or interaction initiation. These modulations do not convey symbolic content. Instead, they serve as perceptual markers that help users attune, orient, anticipate, and emotionally coordinate with the robot's actions and roles.

Within the scope of this paper, these scenarios are not presented as validated applications, but as research hypotheses emerging from an exploratory futuring stage.

Building on this, scent modulation could enhance interaction in assistive contexts where verbal or visual cues are less effective. For example, a service robot might adjust its scent to help visually impaired users orient in time and navigate interaction flow. In care settings involving dementia, differentiated olfactory cues might support routine recognition, reinforce emotional anchoring, or signal attentiveness during moments of agitation. In these ways, scent can contribute not only to identity but also to co-regulation, co-presence, and responsiveness, shaping the shared atmosphere of interaction rather than transmitting explicit messages. Beyond therapeutic contexts, olfactory social robotics can enrich interactions with all users by evoking memories and emotions that foster engagement and

enhance shared social atmospheres. Such potential could also extend to interactions with companion animals, whose highly developed sense of smell might allow them to connect to robots through olfactory cues, fostering familiarity and reducing stress.

8.2 Multisensory Markers and Compatible Otherness

The conceptual and functional role of scent in *ScentDia* offers a generative model for other perceptual markers. Just as olfaction enables the robot to assert a presence that is both distinct and relational, other modalities — tactile, thermal, and visual — can provide complementary anchors for social interaction. Tactile cues such as rhythmic vibration or surface tension might accompany contact or approach. Thermal gradients — with surface temperatures intentionally different from human or animal bodies yet perceptually compatible — can indicate states such as activation, rest, or invitation. For example, a robot might maintain a surface warmth around 30 °C — distinct from human body heat yet socially legible — and modulate it slightly to signal approach, engagement, or withdrawal without mimicking biological cues. Light pulses or movement patterns can also offer alternatives to gaze and gesture, establishing a sensory vocabulary that is recognizably other yet affectively legible.

This approach is particularly valuable in contexts of sensory or cognitive fragility. In a school environment, a neurodiverse child might engage more easily with a robot that uses patterned vibration or light rather than speech or facial mimicry. In elder care, consistent thermal or olfactory cues may offer emotional stability without invoking anthropocentric models of presence. For deaf users, luminous rhythms — clearly distinct from natural sound — can support orientation and interaction in a way that affirms the robot's difference.

These examples show that robotic social presence can be differentiated and adapted not to simulate human interaction, but to establish new forms of relational coordination grounded in perceptual distinction. According to our definition, perceptual markers are not merely decorative but are the material means through which robots become experientiable and intelligible as different, yet socially meaningful agents. Together, these modalities illustrate how perceptual markers can be treated as a transferable design–research framework for constructing and comparing forms of robotic social presence across contexts. Designing for difference — and resisting mimicry — emerges as a central strategy for enabling ethical cohabitation.

8.3 Synthetic Ethics: Perceptual Markers and Experimental Responsibility

The implementation of perceptual markers raises complex ethical issues that cannot be resolved through fixed guidelines or evaluative checklists. What matters is not simply what a robot does, but how its presence is enacted, interpreted, and co-constituted in specific relational contexts. This is where synthetic ethics becomes essential. In this paper, synthetic ethics is not proposed as a normative framework, but as a methodological companion to exploratory, hypothesis-generating research.

As developed in our previous work (e.g., Damiano & Dumouchel, 2026b), synthetic ethics is grounded in the idea that ethical meaning emerges through interaction. It treats human–robot engagement as a space of inquiry in which presence is not only perceived, but also lived, negotiated, and transformed. In the case of perceptual markers, this means not merely assessing the effectiveness of a scent or the recognizability of a thermal cue, but exploring how such signals shape behaviors, rhythms, emotional dispositions, and relationships. What kind of world is being enacted when we live alongside robots that signal socially through scent, warmth, or light? What patterns of co-regulation and expectation do these cues enable or constrain?

Synthetic ethics develops through iterative and situated exploration, accompanying the robot’s entire journey — from design to deployment and integration in target social contexts — as well as the evolution of its social presence. It shifts the focus from theoretical evaluation to pragmatic responsibility. Designers are not asked to anticipate all outcomes, but to remain embedded in iterative, context-sensitive processes of observation and adaptation (e.g., Rajaonah & Zio, 2022). This includes testing how sensory modulation affects users with different vulnerabilities; assessing the emotional and social impact of expressive variation; identifying asymmetries in who configures or controls the robot’s perceptual cues; tracing how differences in perception translate into patterns of inclusion or exclusion.

At its core, synthetic ethics requires abandoning the idea of a neutral design. Every decision — about scent, temperature, rhythm, or timing — contributes to shaping relational dynamics and social imaginaries. Instead of aiming for universal solutions, synthetic ethics promotes the creation of locally robust, ecologically situated, and affectively responsive forms of robotic presence. In this way, it supports not only user well-being, but the emergence of genuinely co-evolved and socially sustainable human–robot relations.

9. Conclusion

This article advances the proposal for an olfactory turn in social robotics. Through the concepts of (a) peri-human design space, (b) perceptual identity markers, and (c) futuring social robotics, we have articulated a paradigm that does not aim at reproducing human features, but at cultivating compatible difference as the basis for sustainable forms of human–robot co-existence. Within this framework, scent has been conceived as a core medium of material and techno-cultural significance through which robotic social presence can be enacted. In biological and cultural contexts, olfaction functions as a scaffold of identity and difference, and, when translated into human–robot social interaction, it defines a powerful perceptual identity marker, rooted in memory, affect, and recognition.

We have engaged this paradigm in *ScentDia*, both as a robotic social actor and as a tool for research. Its olfactory identity, diffusion system, and interactional dynamics translate theoretical principles into an operative case, positioning the robot as a programmatic

instance of olfactory social robotics. Beyond its conceptual grounding, *ScentDia* operated as a situated laboratory: during its premiere and exhibition, it generated qualitative traces of interaction that rendered relational patterns perceptible. Coherently with the futuring methodology presented in *Section 3*, these traces are not intended as validation, but as exploratory hypothesis-generating traces; generative indications that construction itself can function as an instrument of inquiry into human sociality, intersubjectivity, and cohabitation.

This exploratory stance also highlights the limits of the present stage of our research. The field notes we reported do not constitute systematic HRI data. Their value lies instead in opening the domain of olfactory social robotics as a field of inquiry and in orienting the next steps of related research. Building on the recurrent patterns and episodes observed, we have identified a set of prospective lines of inquiry concerning key aspects of human–robot olfactory interaction — including olfactory proxemics, transition-based attribution, and side-by-side co-presence — which we intend to pursue in controlled HRI studies as the next phase of our work.

By positioning *ScentDia* at the intersection of philosophy, art and robotics, we have sought to make available to exploration how synthetic research can anticipate and prototype alternative ecologies of human–robot sociality. Olfactory social robotics, in this perspective, is not simply an application area, but a paradigm for thinking and building *robots with us, not like us*. It invites us to reflect on what new forms of relational life may emerge, and how we may navigate this evolutionary transition responsibly — not by erasing difference, but by designing with it.

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